

Integration of SDGs into Gender-Equitable Spatial Planning in Lhokseumawe City

Nuribadah^{1*}, Hadi Iskandar², Sofyan Jafar³, Satriya Nugraha⁴, Elidar Sari⁵

^{1,2,3,5}Universitas Malikussaleh, Indonesia

⁴Universitas Palangka Raya, Indonesia

*Corresponding Author: nuribadah@unimal.ac.id

ABSTRACT

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This study examines the integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 5 (Gender Equality) and Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), into gender-responsive spatial planning in Lhokseumawe City, Indonesia. Despite national mandates to mainstream SDGs in regional planning, spatial policies at the local level remain largely gender-neutral and insufficiently address socio-ecological vulnerabilities. This research aims to analyze the extent of SDG integration in spatial planning policies and to identify gaps in their implementation. Using a qualitative socio-legal approach, data were collected through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and analysis of policy documents, including the Regional Spatial Planning (RTRW) and related regulations. The findings reveal that while normative frameworks for gender mainstreaming exist, their operationalization in spatial planning remains partial, fragmented, and weakly institutionalized. Key challenges include limited gender-responsive budgeting, insufficient technical guidelines, and weak cross-sectoral coordination. Additionally, environmental pressures, particularly in coastal and water catchment areas, exacerbate spatial inequalities affecting vulnerable groups, especially women. This study contributes to the literature by reconceptualizing spatial planning as a transformative instrument that integrates gender justice and ecological sustainability within the SDG framework. It proposes a policy-oriented framework that embeds gender indicators into spatial planning instruments, strengthens participatory governance, and aligns local planning practices with global sustainability targets. The findings highlight the urgency of shifting from gender-neutral to gender-responsive spatial governance to achieve inclusive and sustainable urban development.

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Introduction

The flash flood of November 25, 2025 showed that Lhokseumawe's previous spatial planning was not fully resilient to hydrometeorological disasters exacerbated by climate change (relevant to SDGs 13, climate change management). Damage to infrastructure such as drainage, bridges, and environmental roads indicates the need for stronger integration of disaster mitigation and adaptation principles in spatial planning. The management and spatial planning of Lhokseumawe City is an important aspect in realizing a clean, beautiful, and orderly urban environment. ¹Cleanliness and order are very crucial issues because clean environmental conditions not only reflect the quality of city governance, but also directly affect the health, comfort, and productivity of the community in carrying out daily activities. A healthy environment is the right of every citizen, so that all people have the same rights and obligations to maintain and realize

¹ <https://www.lhokseumawekota.go.id/berita-VGwoUQ==accessed> February 10, 2025.

it.² This disaster clearly demonstrated how women and children are the most vulnerable groups. Reports from evacuation centers indicate that places like *meunasah* (small mosques) are overflowing with displaced women and children.³ Furthermore, the disruption of health facilities directly jeopardizes the reproductive health of women, pregnant women, and breastfeeding mothers. Therefore, this disaster provides strong justification for implementing gender-sensitive spatial planning (in line with SDG 5: Gender Equality and SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Human Settlements). Planning must be responsive by providing safe public spaces, equal access to post-disaster resources, and infrastructure that takes into account women's specific needs.⁴

One of the main challenges in creating a clean and healthy environment is waste management. Waste becomes a major source of environmental pollution if not managed properly. Therefore, waste management must be carried out consciously, in an integrated, and targeted manner through collaboration between the community and the government. Individual awareness regarding waste disposal and management needs to be supported by an effective and sustainable management system from local governments. Based on estimates from the Lhokseumawe City Sanitation Department, Lhokseumawe produces 90 to 95 tons of waste per day. However, during major holidays or events, waste soars to over 100 tons per day.⁵ However, women's involvement and gender equality are still considered minimal. In practice, due to social norms and gender structural inequalities, women are often marginalized in terms of access and governance, resulting in the goal of a clean and well-organized city not being optimally achieved.

In Indonesia, the commitment to SDG implementation is affirmed through Presidential Regulation No. 59 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goals. This regulation mandates regional governments to integrate SDG principles into development planning documents, including regional spatial plans (RTRW). This aligns with Law No. 26 of 2007 concerning Spatial Planning, which emphasizes that spatial planning aims to create a safe, comfortable, productive, and sustainable national space. Strengthening gender equality in all programs, must be done with all efforts as in the 2020-2024 Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) is an important stage for achieving the goals of the 2005-2025 National Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPN) which is also a starting point for achieving the target of Indonesia's Vision 2045, namely: Advanced Indonesia. In order to carry out the President's Vision and Mission to realize an Advanced Indonesia that is Sovereign, Independent, and Has a Personality Based on Mutual Cooperation.

Presidential Instruction No. 9/2000 and RPJMN 2020-2024, the Strategic Plan (Renstra) of the Ministry of PUPR 2020-2024 contains various policy directions and strategies, goals and objectives of Gender Mainstreaming which serve as the basis for the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing in organizing gender-responsive public works and public housing infrastructure at the Central and Regional levels. Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in National Development emphasizes that gender mainstreaming into all development processes is an inseparable part of the functional activities of all government agencies and institutions at the Central and Regional levels. The 2020-2024 Gender Mainstreaming Implementation Roadmap is a reference for all leaders and staff at the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing at the central and regional levels in implementing gender mainstreaming as an inherent and inseparable part of infrastructure implementation activities to realize gender equality in development, namely development that is fairer and more equitable for all

²UGM, 2025, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Seminar Series #104 "The Future of Indonesia's Low-Carbon Development in the Perspective of Regional Development, p. 1 -

<https://sdgs.geo.ugm.ac.id/2024/09/05/sustainable-development-goals-sdgs-seminar-series-104-masa-depan-pembangunan-rendah-karbon-indonesia-dalam-perspektif-pembangunan-wilayah/>

³Tempo English, 2025, *Sumatra Floods: Families Lost, Houses Razed*, <https://en.tempo.co/read/2072182/sumatra-floods-families-lost-houses-razed>.

⁴https://www.google.com/search?q=tata+ruang+kota+lhokseumawe&rlz=1C1GCEB_enID1189ID1189&oq=tata+ruang+kota+lhokseumawe&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIGCAEQRRg80gEJMTk0OTRqMG00qAIAsAIA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

⁵Darius, Head of Public Relations of Lhokseumawe, 2023, *Lhokseumawe City Government Anticipates Increase in Waste Amount During Apeksi Seminar*, <https://aceh.antaranews.com/berita/347715/pemko-lhokseumawe-antisipasi-jumlah-sampah-naik-saat-sarasehan> apeksi#:~:text=According to%20data%20which%20are%20collected%2C%20per,90%20up%20to%2095%20ton%20sampah.rabu

Indonesian residents, both women and men, including children, youth, the elderly, people with disabilities, Low-Income Communities (MBR) and other vulnerable groups. Gender equality has long been recognized as a human right and a primary goal of development. ⁶The United Nations (UN) has also established a convention as a form of struggle for gender equality, namely the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) in 1979 which has been ratified by 189 countries, including Indonesia. Indonesia ratified the convention through Law Number 7 of 1984 concerning the Ratification of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women. In 2015, the UN also established a program, namely the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), where the fifth goal of the program is "Achieving Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women and Girls." Indonesia also signed the program and then issued Presidential Regulation Number 59 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals which contains national targets based on the goals and targets in the SDGs.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) agenda positions sustainable development as a global paradigm that emphasizes the balance between social, economic, and environmental aspects. ⁷In the urban context, this goal is explicitly reflected in Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Human Settlements) and Goal 5 (Gender Equality), which emphasize the importance of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban planning without leaving vulnerable groups, including women, behind. ⁸The integration of SDGs into regional spatial planning and policies is both a normative and strategic imperative in realizing equitable development. Gender inequality remains a major problem in Indonesia. This gender inequality occurs not only due to traditions and beliefs held by the community, but also due to the systems and regulations implemented, which instill in society the understanding that women's status is lower than that of men. It is not surprising that many policies exist, including those that are detrimental to women.⁹

Essentially, everyone agrees that women and men are different. The distinctions formed in society do not occur naturally but have been constructed over time. Setiadi ¹⁰stated that there is a fundamental difference between gender and sex, with sex referring more to the biological division of human physiology or anatomy. As for the concept of gender, however, in practice, spatial planning is often gender-neutral *and* not fully responsive to the specific needs of men and women. In fact, development policies that do not consider a gender perspective have the potential to result in unequal access to public spaces, city facilities, basic services, and participation in decision-making processes. ¹¹Therefore, gender mainstreaming (PUG) is an important instrument in ensuring that spatial planning is oriented towards social justice and inclusiveness.

This gender inequality does not only occur due to the traditions and beliefs held by the community, but also caused by the system, budget, and rules that are applied to instill an understanding in society that the position of women is lower than that of men. In its development, gender differences will give rise to manifestations of injustice, including marginalization (economic impoverishment) of women, subordination of one gender, negative labeling (*stereotypes*), violence, bearing a greater and longer domestic workload, in general the victims are women with the traditions and beliefs of society that women are in charge and maintain the tidiness of the house, as well as the responsibility for the implementation of all domestic work.¹² From a gender perspective, environmental and urban space management is also closely

⁶Carolyn Frohmader and Stephanie Ortoleva, "The Sexual and Reproductive Rights of Women and Girls With Disabilities", ICPD Beyond, Vol. 1, 2014, p. 4

⁷United Nations, *Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (New York: United Nations, 2015).

⁸ibid

⁹Tilaar and Riant Nugroho, *Educational Policy "Introduction to Understanding Educational Policy and Educational Policy as Public Policy"*, Pustaka Belajar, Yogyakarta: 2012. Page 156

¹⁰Setiadi, EM, & Kolip, U. *Introduction to Sociology: Understanding the Facts and Symptoms of Social Problems: Theory, Application and Solutions*. Kencana. 2011. Page 21.

¹¹Caroline ON Moser, *Gender Planning and Development: Theory, Practice and Training* (London: Routledge, 1993).
<https://www.routledge.com/Gender-Planning-and-Development-Theory-Practice-and-Training/Moser/p/book/9780415056212>

¹²Implementation of Gender Equality in Several Aspects of Community Life in Indonesia Sonny Dewi Judiasih, Padjadjaran University, Bandung, *Acta Diurnal Journal of Notary Law*, Faculty of Law, Padjadjaran University PISSN:

related to women's social roles, particularly in domestic and community contexts. Therefore, gender-unresponsive spatial planning policies have the potential to exacerbate unpaid workloads and social vulnerability. Based on this description, the integration of SDGs into gender-equitable spatial planning in Lhokseumawe City is a strategic issue that requires academic study. This study aims to analyze the extent to which SDG principles, particularly Goal 5 and Goal 11, have been integrated into Lhokseumawe City's spatial planning policies and documents, and their implications for the realization of inclusive, gender-equitable, and sustainable urban development.

Method

The type of research used is sociologically juridical, which can also be called field research, namely examining applicable legal provisions and what occurs in reality in society.¹³This specification is used because this study will describe the principles of the SDGs, particularly Goals 5 and 11, which have been integrated into the policies and spatial planning documents of Lhokseumawe City, as well as their implications for the realization of inclusive, gender-equitable, and sustainable urban development. The data collection method used primary and secondary data.¹⁴By conducting interviews with relevant agencies, secondary data was obtained through literature.¹⁵The primary legal material used was Lhokseumawe Mayor Regulation Number 22 of 2018 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Gender Mainstreaming in Lhokseumawe City. Secondary legal materials were books, journals, and other scientific papers relevant to the issues studied.

Results and Discussion

Integration of SDG Principles, particularly Goal 5 and Goal 11

Integrating SDGs into spatial planning is an approach that aligns a region's spatial plan (such as a city or district) with the targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).¹⁶The goal is to ensure that physical development and spatial management focus not only on economic growth but also on creating an inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable environment for all communities.¹⁷ The integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into regional development planning documents is a national regulatory mandate, which is reinforced through Presidential Regulation Number 111 of 2022 concerning the Implementation of the Achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals.¹⁸ At the local level, Lhokseumawe City demonstrates interesting dynamics in its efforts to integrate SDG principles, particularly Goal 5 (Gender Equality) and Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Human Settlements), into policies and spatial planning documents. However, based on a review of available documents and publications, this integration remains partial, not yet systemic, and faces various implementation challenges.

First, the integration of SDG Goal 5 on Gender Equality. Lhokseumawe already has a policy framework that explicitly adopts the principle of Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) through Mayoral Regulation Number 22 of 2018 concerning Gender Mainstreaming.¹⁹ This regulation serves as the

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<http://jurnal.fh.unpad.ac.id/index.php/acta/issue/archive>

¹³Suharsimi Arikunto, *Research Procedures: A Practical Approach*, Revised Edition 2010, 14th Edition. Jakarta, Rineka Cipta, 2010, p. 12

¹⁴Nauman, L. W. (2015). *Basics of Social Research Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Boston: Pearson. Pl. 25.

¹⁵Ronny Hanitijo Soemitro, *Legal Research Methods and Jurisprudence*, Jakarta, Ghalia. 1994. Page 11

¹⁶Pancasila University, 2020. SDGs Center, Webinar series 1 SDGs 11, page 1.

<https://teknik.univpancasila.ac.id/sdgcen/index.php/2020/06/11/webinar-seri-1-sdgs-11-2/>

¹⁷SDGs Lhokseumawe City, 2025. *Sustainable Cities and Communities*, p. 1 <https://sdgs.jakarta.go.id/sdgs-goal/kota-dan-pemukiman-yang-berkelanjutan>

¹⁸UCLG ASPAC, SDGS Localization Training: Enhance Local Governments' Capacity To Integrate The 2030 Agenda Into Local Policy Documents And Actions, 22 December 2025,

¹⁹Nuribadah, et al, Implementation of Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) in the Clean and Creative City Program in Lhokseumawe, Vol. 1 (2024): Proceedings of Malikussaleh International Conference On Education Social Humanities And Innovation (Miceshi), <https://proceedings.unimal.ac.id/miceshi/issue/view/7>

normative foundation for all development policies, including those related to spatial planning, to be gender responsive. A study by Nuribadah et al. revealed that the implementation of PUG in Lhokseumawe is manifested in the Clean and Creative City Program, in which the local government strives to provide equal opportunities for men and women in the planning, implementation, and maintenance of the city's sanitation infrastructure.²⁰ However, this achievement is still far from ideal. The same research identified three main structural barriers: first, the lack of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) specifically regulating the implementation of gender-sensitive programs; second, budget allocations that are not yet gender-responsive; and third, the low quality of human resources in understanding and implementing gender equality principles. Ironically, an analysis of the Technocratic Draft of the 2024-2029 Lhokseumawe City RPJMD found that there were no work programs that specifically addressed strategic issues in the aspect of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (PPPA).²¹ This gap between normative policies and concrete planning shows that the principles of SDGs 5 have not been systematically integrated into medium-term development planning documents, let alone down to the level of more technical spatial planning documents such as the RDTR.

The Regency/City Spatial Plan (RTRW) is a translation of the national and provincial RTRW into policies and strategies for developing the regency area in accordance with its function and role in the overall regional development plan, where this regional development strategy is then translated into a structural plan and operational spatial pattern plan. In its operationalization, the general spatial plan is described in a detailed spatial plan that is prepared using a strategic value approach to the area and/or regional activities with substantial content that can include the determination of blocks and sub-blocks equipped with zoning regulations as one of the bases for controlling spatial utilization so that spatial utilization can be carried out in accordance with the general spatial plan and detailed spatial plan. The detailed spatial plan can be a strategic area spatial plan and a detailed spatial plan.

Second, the integration of the principles of SDGs Goal 11 on Sustainable Cities and Human Settlements. Of all the search results, the most concrete finding regarding the integration of SDGs 11 in Lhokseumawe's spatial planning comes from documentation of UGM students' internship activities at the Lhokseumawe City Public Works and Housing Agency. The report explicitly states that the process of adjusting the Detailed Spatial Planning Map (RDTR) with the RTRW Map for three Planning Areas (Muara Satu, Muara Dua, and Banda Sakti) is a real contribution to the achievement of SDG 11, particularly in the target of creating safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and communities.²² Technical activities such as attribute data improvement, map overlays, and manual selection based on notes from cross-agency meetings, while seemingly procedural, are fundamental steps in realizing quality spatial planning. Furthermore, efforts to preserve mangrove ecosystem zones and provide green open spaces accommodated in the Lhokseumawe RDTR not only support SDG 15 (Terrestrial Ecosystems) but are also key indicators of SDG 11, which emphasizes the provision of public spaces and the protection of natural and cultural heritage.²³

At the development vision level, the integration of sustainability principles is also evident in strategic planning documents. The Lhokseumawe City Long-Term Development Vision for 2025-2045, "Lhokseumawe Islamic, Independent, Advanced, and Sustainable," explicitly includes the word "Sustainable." This keyword is interpreted normatively as "development in accordance with the carrying capacity and capacity of the environment, the resilience of the community and city to disasters, and social, cultural, and economic resilience." This interpretation has a strong conceptual alignment with the SDG 11 framework. The vision was then translated into the 2025-2029 RPJMD as "Realizing Lhokseumawe as a Smart and Comfortable City to Live in," where the word "Smart" is interpreted to realize "Advanced" and "Comfortable to Live in" to realize "Sustainable". Development is not just about numbers and targets,

²⁰ibid

²¹Rayhan Ali, Review of the Technocratic Design of the 2024-2029 Lhokseumawe City RPJMD, *Institute for Inclusive Cities Envisioning our future cities*, <https://i2cities.org/review-rancangan-teknokratik-rpjmd-kota-lhokseumawe-2024-2029/>

²²Public Relations of SIG UGM, 2024, Contribution of SIG UGM Students in the Preparation of the Lhokseumawe City RDTR: Realizing Sustainable Spatial Planning.

<https://sig.sv.ugm.ac.id/kontribusi-mahasiswa-sig-ugm-dalam-penyusunan-rdtr-kota-lhokseumawe-mewujudkan-tata-ruang-berkelanjutan/>

²³ibid.

but also about how a city treats the waste of its citizens' activities. With the *Broeh Jeut Keu Peng* program, the Lhokseumawe City government affirms its commitment that waste is not the end, but the beginning of transformation. Concrete policies and steps transform waste into value, shifting the paradigm from mere disposal to managing and empowering, starting with the Alue Lim Landfill, a space once synonymous with the end of the world that has now become a symbol of sustainable change born from the courage to manage what has long been considered to be based on responsibility, innovation, and the future of the city.²⁴ The author hopes that gender perspectives will not be ignored, but rather consciously integrated into every stage of implementation. *Broeh Jeut Keu Peng* provides equal participation for women and men, both in management, training, decision-making, and the utilization of economic outcomes from waste processing. Women, who have often been at the forefront of household waste management, are empowered through capacity building, access to business opportunities, and protection and recognition for their contributions. With this inclusive approach, the program not only creates economic value from waste but also promotes social justice and equal opportunity. The transformation being built is not merely an environmental transformation, but also a transformation of perspective that sustainable development must be inclusive of all, leaving no one behind.

The authority of Lhokseumawe City Qanun Number 9 of 2015 concerning Waste Management, in its considerations, states that Islamic teachings prioritize cleanliness, beauty, and order, so that these are aspects of life that need to be maintained continuously and together, both by the Lhokseumawe City Government and by the community itself, in order to realize a clean, orderly and healthy environment. That the growth of the population of Lhokseumawe City has resulted in an increasingly diverse and increasing volume of waste produced daily, so that it requires integrated waste management by involving the participation of the community and the business world in a comprehensive manner. proportional, effective, efficient, and culturally sound. Furthermore, Article 3 explains that waste management aims to improve public health standards, environmental quality and cleanliness, and to transform waste into an economically valuable resource.

Women's participation and empowerment are two crucial issues in development programs. *The International Union for Conservation of Nature* (IUCN) states that women play a key role in the use and management of natural resources, particularly in agriculture and forest landscape systems along the value chain. According to IUCN (2021), in developing countries, 43% of women are involved in agricultural work and depend on forests for their livelihoods. The same data estimates that when women have equal access to productive resources as men, they can contribute to increasing agricultural yields in developing countries by 2.5% to 4%. Women's global involvement has implications for reducing world hunger by 12% to 17%. Women's involvement in forest access and governance has been shown to improve the economic well-being of women and communities surrounding forest areas.²⁵

The development of gender equality issues in developing countries like Indonesia is inseparable from the development of gender equality issues globally. According to the 2021 *Global Gender Gap Report*, Indonesia ranks 101st out of 156 countries with a score of 0.688, down 16 places from the previous year (World Economic Forum 2021). *This gender gap* ranking is measured through four indicators: (1) economic participation and opportunity; (2) educational attainment; (3) health and survival; and (4) political empowerment (World Economic Forum 2021). By considering these indicators in measuring the gender gap, the realization of gender equality in Indonesia is highly relevant to economic development, not merely a matter of morality and justice.²⁶

Women's access to the implementation of K3 and access to technology and information and various other resources is less than men, women are underrepresented and have less influence in public decision-making in leadership positions within government institutions, and women bear the burden of household care and are underrepresented in mitigation programs and initiatives related to environmental change issues. The struggles of women in the past continue to this day. The quality of life for women in Indonesia

²⁴Seuramo Rakyat Kota, 2026, *Not Talking Broeh Jeut Keu Peng*, was inaugurated in Lhokseumawe City.

https://www.tiktok.com/@seuramoerakyatkota/video/7605502191675133202?is_from_webapp=1&sender_device=pc

²⁵ Girl, Arivia, Women and Social Forestry, *WOMEN'S JOURNAL Vol . 27* No. 1 April 2022 Issue 111, [https://catalog.danlevlibrary.net/index.php?p=show_detail&id=18821&keywords =](https://catalog.danlevlibrary.net/index.php?p=show_detail&id=18821&keywords=)

²⁶ *ibid*

is not entirely encouraging, as gaps in the quality of life between men and women persist, particularly in crucial aspects of human life, such as health, education, and the economy.²⁷ Women's voices are needed in key decision-making positions to ensure that the resulting decisions and policies are more favorable to women and children, thereby eliminating the disparity in the quality of life between men and women. Therefore, it is crucial to enhance women's leadership capacity so that they become more confident in participating and voicing their aspirations in various stages of the development process, from the national level down to village government. Many women have already become agents of change, and it is hoped that even more Indonesian women will become agents of change, boldly initiating change within themselves, their families, and their communities for the better. The aim is to realize gender equality and justice, so that it can be implemented through gender-responsive planning, gender-responsive budgeting in accordance with Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in National Development, which emphasizes that Gender Mainstreaming into the entire development process is an integral part, separate from the functional activities of all government agencies and institutions at the central and regional levels.

Roadmap is a reference for all leaders and staff at the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing at the Central and Regional levels in implementing gender mainstreaming as an inherent and inseparable part of infrastructure implementation activities to realize gender equality in development. With the Regent's Decree Number: 08 / Renstra-PP,PA,PP & KB / 2022 concerning the Office of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, Population Control and Family Planning, Lhokseumawe City, mainstreaming is essential for the implementation of a gender-responsive budget in every technical regional government agency (OPD). To ensure gender-responsive budgeting, *the Gender Analysis Pathway* (GAP) and *Gender Budget Statement* (GBS) will be used in each technical agency. Providing gender- and child-disaggregated data is crucial for improving community well-being. The availability of data facilitates planning and budgeting based on needs. Qanun Number Qanun of Lhokseumawe City Number 1 of 2014 concerning the Spatial Planning of Lhokseumawe City, Article 67 concerning the Implementation of spatial planning is carried out by the government by involving various elements such as the community, private parties, the business world, professional groups, NGOs, hereinafter referred to as the role of the community, has rights and obligations in spatial planning, both at the stage of preparing spatial plans, spatial utilization, and the stage of controlling spatial utilization.

In Lhokseumawe City, understanding gender mainstreaming is a top priority for policymakers. The goal is for development policies to promote equal access, participation, control, and benefits for all members of society. This strategy is implemented through Gender Responsive Planning and Budgeting (PPRG), in accordance with Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in National Development. This requires a tool *known* as Gender Responsive Planning and Budgeting (PPRG). Planning and Budgeting. Gender-responsive planning is planning to achieve gender equality and justice, which is carried out through the integration of the experiences, aspirations, needs, potentials and problem solving of women and men. In Aceh Province, gender integration has been regulated in Aceh Governor Regulation Number 6 of 2014 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Gender-Responsive Planning and Budgeting which mandates Aceh Work Units to prepare planning documents using *the gender analysis pathway* (GAP) and *gender budget statement* (GBS) methods.

The implication is the realization of inclusive, gender-equitable and sustainable urban development

The flash flood disaster of November 25, 2025, in Lhokseumawe City was not merely a hydrometeorological event; it opened up a new discursive space in post-disaster urban planning. This event forced the local government to no longer position gender and sustainability issues as normative discourse, but rather as the primary foundation of urban reconstruction. The most fundamental implication of integrating the SDGs and a gender perspective is the transformation of the development approach from a reactive to an anticipatory-responsive one. This aligns with the build-back-better principle, which

²⁷Agustina Ern, 2020, Realizing Equality Through Increasing Women's Leadership Capacity, Deputy for Gender Equality, Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (Kemen PPPA), Press Release Number: B-295/Set/Rokum/MP 01/11/2020, <https://www.kemenpppa.go.id/index.php/page/read/29/2935/wujudkan-kesetaraan-dengan-peningkatan-kapasitas-kepemimpinan-perempuan>

requires improving the quality of infrastructure and social outcomes post-disaster, not simply restoring them to their original state.²⁸In the context of gender justice, disasters have demonstrated how socially constructed vulnerability exacerbates the impact of disasters on women. Therefore, post-disaster spatial planning must be able to transform power relations in access to and control of urban resources. Women's meaningful participation in the formulation of Regional Spatial Plans (RTRW) and Detailed Spatial Plans (RDTR) is an absolute prerequisite for ensuring that public infrastructure such as evacuation areas, health facilities, and mobilization routes are not gender-neutral, but rather responsive to the specific needs of women, the elderly, and people with disabilities.²⁹ The integration of the principles of SDGs Goals 5 and 11 can be analyzed through a sustainable development perspective that emphasizes the balance of social, economic, and environmental aspects combined with a Gender and Development approach that highlights power relations and gender equality in development, as well as *the Right to the City concept* that emphasizes the rights of all citizens to space and participation in urban planning.³⁰ Furthermore, the sustainability dimension in post-flood Lhokseumawe city development must be oriented towards simultaneously strengthening ecological and social resilience. SDG 11 (*Sustainable Cities and Communities*) and SDG 13 (*Climate Action*) demand spatial planning policies that integrate ecosystem-based disaster mitigation, such as protecting water catchment areas and rehabilitating the Krueng Pasee watershed, which serves as the upstream floodwater. This policy must be accompanied by guarantees of equitable access for all residents to green open spaces and disaster-resilient basic infrastructure³¹. Sustainability also means breaking the cycle of structural poverty exacerbated by disasters, by restoring women's livelihoods in the informal sector, agriculture, and fisheries through affirmative economic recovery programs (SDG 1 and SDG 8).³²

Thus, the long-term implication of this disaster is the creation of political momentum to institutionalize inclusive urban planning. If planned in a participatory and equitable manner, post-disaster reconstruction has the potential to produce a new spatial plan that is not only resilient to climate shocks but also able to serve as an instrument of correction for gender inequality and social vulnerability that have long been structured in the urban space of Lhokseumawe. Sustainable urban development is no longer interpreted only as economic growth and physical development, but also includes social and environmental dimensions in an integrated manner. In this context, the Broeh Jeut Keu Peng program initiated by the Lhokseumawe City Government is one example of development practices that integrate environmental management with community empowerment. The transformation of waste management that began at the Alue Lim landfill demonstrates a paradigm shift from mere waste disposal to value-added management.

This approach aligns with the concept of sustainable development introduced in the World Commission on Environment and Development's *Common Future report*, which emphasizes that development must meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.³³The circular economy-based waste management in this program reflects this principle, as waste is viewed as a reusable resource, not merely a final residue. Furthermore, the integration of a gender perspective into this program strengthens its inclusive development dimension. The concept of gender mainstreaming, as emphasized by the United Nations through the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), emphasizes the importance of ensuring that the experiences and needs of women and men are an integral part of the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public policies.³⁴In the context of household waste management, women often play a central role, making their empowerment through training, economic access, and participation in decision-making a strategic step

²⁸United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), *Build Back Better: In Recovery, Rehabilitation and Reconstruction* (Geneva: UNDRR, 2021), p. 15-18

²⁹Prianti, A., & Sari, N. P, Women's Participation in Spatial Planning with a Gender Perspective in Urban Areas, *Journal of Urban and Regional Planning*, Vol. 33, No. 2 (2022), pp. 145-160.

³⁰Moser, CON (1993). *Gender planning and development: Theory, practice and training*. London: Routledge.

³¹Regulation of the Minister of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning/Head of the National Land Agency Number 16 of 2020 concerning Procedures for Preparing Spatial Planning that Takes into Account Disaster Aspects

³²United Nations Development Program (UNDP), *Gender Equality in Recovery and Reconstruction: Building Back Better for Women and Girls* (New York: UNDP, 2023), p. 34.

³³World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1987), p. 43

³⁴United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), *Agreed Conclusions 1997/2 on Gender Mainstreaming*.

towards gender equity. The implications of this approach are significant. First, in terms of inclusivity, the program opens up participation for various community groups, including women and local communities previously under-involved in environmental policy. Active community participation is a principle of sustainable development governance, reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 11 on inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and human settlements.³⁵

The issue of gender equality and gender justice has become a global issue that is increasingly receiving attention and is part of global agreements concerning human rights, because in reality, women have experienced discrimination that violates human rights and respect for women as human beings. Until now, demands for women's representation in various decision-making institutions continue to develop and are considered important. Because in reality, various problems that arise in various fields and in various parts of the world cannot be separated from the problem of the still dominant discriminatory treatment against women so that poverty, education, health, unemployment and even various acts of violence are very vulnerable to making women victims of this discrimination. The term gender was first introduced by Robert Hellen, who distinguished between human characteristics based on sociocultural definitions and those based on physical, biological characteristics. Ann Oakley similarly stated that gender is a difference in human nature that is neither biological nor divinely ordained.³⁶ We often misunderstand gender and women's issues. When we talk about gender, it's often seen as a women's issue, one that must be addressed and resolved solely by women.³⁷

Second, from a gender equity perspective, women's integration into the waste management value chain strengthens access to economic resources and increases bargaining power within households and communities. Women's economic empowerment has been shown to have a positive correlation with improving family welfare and reducing poverty.^[4] Thus, this program not only impacts the environment but also social transformation.³⁸ Opy Trisnawan, Gender is part of the social system, like social status, age, and ethnicity, it is an important factor in determining the roles, rights, responsibilities, and relationships between men and women.³⁹ Gender is a social construct or form that is not inherently innate, so its implementation in practice can be shaped or changed depending on location or region, time, culture, social status, religious understanding, state ideology, politics, law, and economics.⁴⁰ According to Hungu, gender is the biological difference between women and men that exists from birth.⁴¹ The biological differences and functions of men and women are not interchangeable, and their functions remain the same for all men and women on earth.⁴² Gender is not immutable or divinely ordained, but rather a human-made creation based on the cultural conditions of a given place. Restrictions on women's civil liberties to the private sphere, in addition to traditional restrictions on movement, speech, awareness, and family freedom, remain outside the scope of human rights concerns.⁴³ It is further emphasized that the term Gender is "a social construction of the roles of men and women as demanded by society and played by each of them."⁴⁴ Third, from an environmental sustainability perspective, reducing the volume of waste sent to landfills contributes to reduced pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Responsible waste

³⁵United Nations, *Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*, 2015 (SDG 11).

³⁶Rasyidin, 2016, *Gender and Politics: Women's Representation in Politics* (Banda Aceh: Unimal Press, pp. 16-17)

³⁷Lusia Palulungan, et al. (2017). *Strengthening Women for Justice and Equality*. Makassar: Eastern Indonesia Knowledge Exchange Foundation (BaKTI)

³⁸World Bank, *World Development Report 2012: Gender Equality and Development*.

³⁹ Opy Trisnawati, Subhan Widiyansyah, Gender Equality Towards Women in the Field of Education in Higher Education (*J-Psh*) *Journal of Sociology and Humanities Education* Volume 13 Number 2 October 2022 Page 339-347/ E-Issn: 2715-1247 And P-Issn: 2087-84xx <https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/Index.Php/Jpsh/Index> 339 10.26418/J-Psh.V13i2.54606. Page 39.

⁴⁰AlifiahUtaminingsih, (2017). *Gender and Career Women*. UB Press: Malang, p. 5.

⁴¹Op.cit. Opy Trisnawati <https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/index.php/JPSH/article/download/54606/75676593700>

⁴²Juwita Pratiwi, 2024. Women's Empowerment as the Main Axis of Sustainable Development: Building Equality, Welfare, and Environmental Balance. *Journal of International Multidisciplinary Research*. Vol. 2. No. 8, 2024. *Women's Empowerment as the Main Axis of Sustainable Development: Building Equality, Welfare, and Environmental Balance* . <https://doi.org/10.62504/jimr822>

⁴³See, UNIFEM CEDAW South-East Asia Programme, "Restoring Rights to Women" Partners for Law in Development (PLD), New Delhi, Jakarta, June 2007

⁴⁴Wardah Hafidz, *Glossary of Gender Terms*, Office of the Minister of State for Women's Affairs, Jakarta 1995, p. 5.

management practices are an essential part of local climate change mitigation strategies.⁴⁵ By simultaneously integrating environmental, social, and gender dimensions, the Broeh Jeut Keu Peng program contributes to inclusive, gender-equitable, and sustainable urban development. This model demonstrates that sustainability stems not only from technical innovation but also from the courage to implement policies responsive to social justice and equality.

Capacity building is a process of improving or changing the behavior of individuals, organizations, and community systems to achieve predetermined goals effectively and efficiently. According to Syahyuti,⁴⁶ *capacity building* is an effort to strengthen a community by starting from the richness of their values and priority needs and organizing them to do it themselves. Capacity building acts as a tool or instrument that supports the efficient use of existing potential and capacity, expanding existing potential conditions, and also in the form of awakening new potential. Capacity building also focuses on issues of economic, social, and political relations.⁴⁷ In addition, Indonesia has also established a gender mainstreaming strategy, which was confirmed in Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming. Gender Mainstreaming (PUG) in development is implemented through two main strategies: gender analysis and Communication, Information, and Education (KIE) efforts. Gender analysis aims to identify the existence or absence of gaps and injustices between men and women, understand the causal factors, and formulate appropriate solutions.⁴⁸ This activity includes assessing differences in access, participation, benefits, and control over development policies and programs, developing strategic steps to achieve equality, and establishing gender indicators as a measurement tool for achievement. Gender equality is included in the goals that must be achieved in long-term and medium-term national development.⁴⁹ Therefore, both women and men have equal opportunities and access as agents of development.⁵⁰

The living environment as stated in Law Number 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management is a unity of space with all objects, power, conditions and living creatures, including humans and their behavior, which affect nature itself, the continuity of life, and the welfare of humans and other living creatures. A polluted environment will result in fatal things for humans, for example water polluted by liquid waste from factories, air polluted by the amount of vehicle smoke and factory smoke, and also waste originating from medical facilities will cause diseases including cancer, nervous system disorders, hepatitis, liver swelling and symptoms of depression. In relation to the rights and obligations of the community, Article 24 of Lhokseumawe City Law Number 9 of 2015 states that everyone has the right to receive good, correct, and environmentally friendly waste management services from the city government and/or waste management service providers. The community also has the right to participate in the decision-making process, implementation, and supervision in the field of waste management. In addition, the community has the right to obtain correct, accurate, and timely information regarding the implementation of waste management, receive protection and compensation for the negative impacts arising from TPA activities, and receive guidance to be able to carry out waste management properly and environmentally.⁵¹ Lhokseumawe City faces environmental challenges, including inadequate waste management and waste disposal, both solid and liquid. Liquid waste issues include medical waste, which is still poorly managed. A city's waste management aims to address the waste generated by its residents, indirectly contributing to public health and creating a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment.

⁴⁵United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), *Global Waste Management Outlook*, 2015.

⁴⁶<https://files.osf.io/v1/resources/vyb4k/providers/osfstorage/5bdec974954c620019e64fdb?action=download&direct&version=1>

⁴⁷Jaka Ramdani, 2025, *Inclusivity Study in the Perspective of Green Social Work*, *Jurnal Publikitas*, <https://doi.org/10.37858/publisitas.v1i2.551>

⁴⁸Laila Kholid Alfirdaus, 2019, Sharpening Gender Perspectives, Empowering Women and Achieving the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), *Egalita, Journal of Gender Equality and Justice*, Vol. 13, No. 1, <https://doi.org/10.18860/egalita.v13i1.8076>.

⁴⁹Retno Kusumawiranti, 2021, *Gender Mainstreaming and Social Inclusion in Village Development*, p. 21. <https://doi.org/10.37631/POPULIKA.V9I1.348>

⁵⁰Indiani Eka Saputri, et al., 2024. Challenges and Realization of Gender Equality as a Social Reality and Its Implications for Development in Indonesia, <https://doi.org/10.33503/maharsi.v6i1.3997>

⁵¹Wartoyo, *Contextualization of Gender Equality in Sustainable Economic Development from an Islamic Economic Perspective*, *el-jizya Journal of Islamic Economics*, Vol. 14 No. 1 2022, 2. Pl. 211 ; <https://ejournal.uinsaizu.ac.id/index.php/eljizya>

Currently, waste management faces significant pressure, particularly due to the increasing volume of waste generated by both producers and consumers. All waste from its respective sources will end up in the Alue Lim landfill. Waste sources are typically divided into two broad categories: *residential* or household waste; *and* non-residential waste, similar to household waste, such as from markets, commercial establishments, and so on.⁵² Issues and problems affecting women and children are complex and cross-sectoral. They are complex because many interrelated factors contribute to the poor quality of life for women and children. They are also called cross-sectoral because the problems are present in nearly all sectors, and therefore, addressing these issues requires the involvement of all development sectors.⁵³ It is emphasized that anyone who owns or controls a building or land/open field suspected of being a place or source of waste is required to equip or provide trash bins with a size capable of accommodating waste originating from the waste source and in appropriate shape and placed in a place that is easily accessible and removed.⁵⁴ The Lhokseumawe City Government involves women in cleanliness, beautification, and order activities. Women play a role as educators for families and the environment to realize gender equality. Support facilities such as trash bins and transportation are provided to support their role in creating a clean and comfortable environment.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of Lhokseumawe City's policies and planning documents, two main conclusions can be drawn. First, the integration of SDGs principles, particularly Goal 11 (Sustainable City), has been realized through the RPJMK 2025–2029 vision as a "Smart and Livable City" which is outlined in priority programs such as flood management, waste management, and the provision of green open spaces 1-5. Second, the implementation of Goal 5 (Gender Equality) is still implicit, although commitment to inclusivity is demonstrated through the provision of sign language interpreters in planning forums and strengthening women's capacity in SDGs 1-3. The implication is that inclusive and sustainable city development has begun to be realized, but gender mainstreaming still requires more explicit policy strengthening in future spatial planning documents.⁵⁵

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⁵²Khennita Zulfavia, Head of Planning for Aceh Special Region Development and Human Resources, *interview* , November 1, 2023.

⁵³Women's Involvement Strategy in Slum-Free Urban Development in Bireuen Regency
Nuribadah, <https://journal.stianasional.ac.id/index.php/humanis/article/view/151/181>

⁵⁴ *Op.cit.* Darius. , <https://aceh.antarane.ws.com/berita/347715/pemko-lhokseumawe-antisipasi-jumlah-sampah-naik-saat-sarasehan> apeksi#:~:text=According to%20data%20which%20are%20collected%2C%20per,90%20up%20to%2095%20ton%20sampah.rabu

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